

Using Decision Tree Classification Models to Predict Payment Type in NYC Yellow Taxi

Hadeer Ismaeil¹, Manal A.Abdel-Fattah², Sherif Kholeif³

Faculty of Computers and Artificial Intelligence
Helwan University, Egypt

hgado92@gmail.com¹, manal_8@hotmail.com², sherifkholeif@yahoo.com³

Abstract— The taxi services are growing rapidly as reliable services. The demand and competition between service provider are so high. A billion trip records need to be analyzed to raise the spirit of competition, understand the service user, and improve the business. Although decision tree classification is common algorithm, there is no implementation for classification on taxi dataset. This research applies the decision tree classification model on taxi dataset to classify instances correctly, build a decision tree, and calculate accuracy. This experiment collected decision tree algorithm with Spark framework to present the good performance and high accuracy when predicting payment type.

Index Terms— Big data analytics; Apache Spark; Decision tree; Taxi trips; Classification; Spark ML; Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Big data describes the large volume of data, but there's no rule strictly defines the size of data. What really determines that the data is big, is the need for multiple physical or virtual devices to process this data as fast as possible. [1] this data is generated by everything around us like systems, digital devices, and remote sensors. Big data is used for collecting and analyzing large and complex data sets to produce knowledge. In the past, storing, processing, and analyzing this volume of data were a problem; but new technologies solved this problem.

One of the tools that are used to analyze data is Apache Spark, which is open-source data analytics tools. Spark is based on MapReduce, but it's faster as it stores the data in the memory into RDD (Resilient Distributed Databases). [3]

Fig. 1: Spark and Hadoop Performance. [3]

When talking about machine learning, Spark has two types of machine learning libraries: Spark MLlib, and Spark ML. Spark MLlib is the original API and it is based on RDD API, so it has more features than the new API (Spark ML). Spark ML provides high-level API, and it is based on data frames and dataset; it supports pipeline and easier to construct. Spark MLlib focuses on the basics of the algorithm leaving data preparation and pipelines to the user, but Spark ML works on all those aspects from data preparation to model training. Spark MLlib is the best choice when dealing with a stream of data. The new features will be added to Spark ML and this why we will use Spark ML. [4]

Spark ML is based on pipeline concept which uses different stages to perform separate tasks from data cleaning to feature selection and applying machine learning algorithm. Pipeline stages consist of two basics transformers and estimators. Transformers use *transform* method which takes a data set as input and returns an enhanced dataset as a result. Estimators, when fit, returns a transform, it uses the *fit* method on data set to produce a model. A decision tree is an estimator that trains dataset to produce a model. [4]

Classification is an important technique for assigning a data object to predefined class or category. One of the most commonly used algorithms, used to apply a classification technique, is the Decision tree algorithm. Decision tree one of the important algorithms in Classification technique. It builds a tree model. Decision tree algorithm is popular because it's easy to implement and understand. In addition, it is simple and fast to construct compared to other classification algorithms.

Decision tree algorithms extract knowledge from data and present it graphically. The most common used decision tree algorithms are ID3, C4.5, and CART. C4.5 is an improved version of ID3. [5]

Transportation plays a vital role in our life especially Taxi and Car services. As a business, it is a huge industry. Every minute there is a hundred of trips from just a single zone, which create a huge amount of data [6] [7]. NYC Taxi and Limousine commission provides an open Dataset that includes detailed trip record from NYC yellow taxi through 2017. Predicting payment method is considered important to business. Customers add their credit card only in trusted services. The greater the number of registered or used credit cards, the higher the service reliability is. It is also important to the driver to know the payment method as some drivers

prefer cash and others prefer credit for guaranteed payment. We can use this dataset to predict a lot of things like passenger count, Hotspot to reduce peak factor, Rush hour for extra charges and high demand at a specific time.

II. RELATED WORK

In [8], S. Singh, et. al. studied and compared the most popular decision tree algorithms, ID3, C4.5, and CART. The survey described the advantage and disadvantage of each algorithm. The survey also contains a comparison between characteristics of each algorithm like the type of data suitable for each algorithm, speed, dealing with missing values and splitting formula. It also shows some application of decision tree such as business, industry, medicine and so on. Common datasets, tools, and problems of decision tree were introduced. The final observation of the survey was the dependency of splitting formula and dataset feature with the performance of the algorithm.

In [9], H. Sun, et. al. described how taxi data was collected through sensors and GPS. They analyzed taxi data to extract and filter data to get a valuable information and results. The results from analysis helped them propose a new application that adds new benefits to the taxi passengers and drivers. They described data attributes and how they used big-data tools to extract useful information, so they can notice relations between attributes. The analysis steps were described briefly to produce analysis results and patterns that was helpful to their mobile service.

In [10], X. Meng, et. al. discussed MLlib (machine learning library) and the need of this library to benefit from the great wealth of data nowadays. They described how spark is efficient with machine learning algorithms as it is iterative in nature. They also discussed other advantages of integrating MLlib with Spark. They presented the history of spark and MLlib development. They discussed briefly core features, performance, Scalability, and continuous improvements of MLlib library.

In [11], S. Salloum, et. al. presented the importance of big data analytics, Spark framework, and how Spark was initiated. They also presented the core features of Spark, Spark Components, how Apache Spark is perfect when dealing with iterative analysis and algorithms, and Apache Spark case studies in industry. They described Spark API's and Libraries and compared different libraries, compared machine learning packages (spark.ml and spark. MLlib), and the use of each of them. Other features and packages were introduced like Graph analysis, stream processing, batch streaming, and interactive analytics.

III. DATASET

TABLE I
DATA DICTIONARY

Attribute Name	Description
VendorID	A code indicating the TPEP provider that provided the record. 1= Creative Mobile Technologies, LLC; 2= VeriFone Inc.

tpep_pickup_datetime	The date and time when the meter was engaged, it was categorized based on hour interval 0:3 = a; 4:7=b; 8:11=c; 12:15=d; 16:19=e; 20:23=f.
tpep_dropoff_datetime	The date and time when the meter was disengaged, it was categorized based on hour interval 0:3 = a; 4:7=b; 8:11=c; 12:15=d; 16:19=e; 20:23=f.
Passenger_count	The number of passengers in the vehicle. The driver enters this value.
Trip_distance	The elapsed trip distance in miles reported by the taximeter.
PULocationID	TLC Taxi Zone in which the taximeter was engaged
DOLocationID	TLC Taxi Zone in which the taximeter was disengaged
RateCodeID	The final rate code in effect at the end of the trip. 1= Standard rate 2=JFK 3=Newark 4=Nassau or Westchester 5=Negotiated fare 6=Group ride
Store_and_fwd_flag	This flag indicates whether the trip record was held in vehicle memory before it is sent to the vendor, aka "store and forward," because the vehicle did not have a connection to the server. Y= store and forward trip N= not a store and forward trip
Payment_type	A numeric code signifying how the passenger paid for the trip. 1= Credit card 2= Cash 3= No charge 4= Dispute 5= Unknown 6= Voided trip
Fare_amount	The time-and-distance fare calculated by the meter.
Extra	Miscellaneous extras and surcharges. Currently, this only includes the \$0.50 and \$1 rush hour and overnight charges.
MTA_tax	\$0.50 MTA tax that is automatically triggered based on the metered rate in use
Improvement_surcharge	\$0.30 improvement surcharge assessed trips at the flag drop. The improvement surcharge began being levied in 2015
Tip_amount	Tip amount – This field is automatically populated for credit card tips. Cash tips are not included, this column was categorized: 0.0 = no tips; 1.0 = tips
Tolls_amount	Total amount of all tolls paid in trip.
Total_amount	The total amount charged to passengers (Does not include cash tips)

The dataset describes yellow taxi trips throughout January 2017. NYC Taxi and Limousine Commission (TLC) shares a billion of data through their website. [12]

This data was collected by technology providers authorized under the Taxicab & Livery Passenger Enhancement Programs (TPEP/LPEP) and provided to NYC Taxi and Limousine Commission. This data was not generated but collected from real life. Our dataset contains 1048575 trip records. Each trip record contains a timestamp for pickup and drop-off, the id of the vendor that provided the record, pickup and drop-off location, passenger count, trip distance, payment type and detailed information about the amount paid by the passengers.

IV. DATA PREPARATION

In the dataset, first, we removed the total amount column because this column has a high correlation with other columns. Second, we removed the Improvement_surcharge column because it has a constant value. Third, pickupDateTime and dropoffDateTime are timestamp column with millions of unique instances so we need to divide it into categories and each category has a range of hours.

Fig. 2: The framework of applying decision tree algorithm on taxi data.

V. CLASSIFICATION ON SPARK

In [13] K. Zhao, et. al. they analyzed Uber and yellow taxi samples in NYC using three predictors: Neural Network, Markov predictor, and Lempel-Ziv-Welch predictors. They calculated accuracy based on different features; Neural Network was the only machine learning based method used in this comparison. Until now, there are not enough research papers applied in this dataset. Although Classification achieved good accuracy when applied in different applications like healthcare and business [14] [15] [16], and also decision tree was used in different applications and achieved high accuracy [5] [17], decision tree classification was not applied on taxi dataset yet. Based on those previous researches we will use decision tree classification with Apache Spark tool to calculate the accuracy of prediction. In this research, we used Java language to apply classification algorithm on Apache Spark. We used Spark version 2.2.1. When applying classification algorithm on taxi dataset, some issues appeared; some are related to the data as it needs some preparation before executing the algorithm and the others are related to the algorithm. After data preparation, we do the following steps to apply the classification algorithm to NYC taxi dataset:

1. Load the data stored in JSON format.
2. Use “StringIndexerModel” to index labels and add metadata to the label column.
3. Identify and index categorical feature.
4. Split the data into training and test sets of data.
5. Set Decision tree model
6. Convert Indexed Labels to original labels
7. Use Pipeline to chain indexer and tree.
8. Start training model and make prediction
9. Compute test errors and accuracy.

VI. RESULTS

This model was executed in 5 minutes and 7.823 seconds. The algorithm was applied on 8GB Ram and 2 GHz processor core i7. The resulted accuracy of this model is 96.5%.

We will use another evaluation metrics to evaluate this algorithm. There are four main categories that are used to calculate these metrics. In a supervised classification problem, there exists a true output and a predicted or model generated output. Therefore, the result of each data point will be assigned to one of the following categories:

- True Positive (TP): label is positive, and prediction is positive.
- True Negative (TN): label is negative, and prediction is negative.
- False Positive (FP): label is negative, but prediction is positive.
- False negative (FN): label is positive, but prediction is negative.

These four categories are the basics for most classification evaluation metrics. Metrics like precision and recall take into account the type of

error, while F-measure captures the balance between precision and recall and combine them to calculate F-measure. Precision (Positive Predictive Value) measures how many selected items from the dataset are relevant, while recall (True Positive Rate) measure how many relevant items are selected. For Example, if our dataset contains 100 taxi trips containing 75 trips that were paid by credit cards and 25 trips were paid in cash. And let’s suppose an algorithm for detecting credit card payment type identifies 60 trips paid with credit card, 55 were actually paid with a credit card (true positive) while the rest was paid in cash (false positive). Using the following formula, we can calculate precision ($PPV = 55/60 = 0.92$) and recall ($TPR = 60/75 = 0.8$). High precision means that the algorithm returned relevant results more than irrelevant ones (from 60 trips the returned 55 that are really paid with credit card). High recall means that the algorithm returns most of the relevant results (there were 75 trips paid with a credit card in the dataset, but the algorithm identified only 55 trips).

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (1)$$

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{P} = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (2)$$

$$F = 2 \cdot \frac{\text{precision} \cdot \text{recall}}{\text{precision} + \text{recall}} \quad (3)$$

In binary classification, there are only two possible class labels. However, in Multiclass classification there are many class labels as in our dataset payment type are classified from 1 to 6 digits having 6 possible classes. Precision and recall are calculated for each class label then we calculate weighted precision, recall, and F-measure. The following table compares accuracy, test error, weighted precision, weighted recall, and weighted F-measure when changing the splitting criteria of the data into training and testing set. In the first case, 10% of data was held for testing. In the Second case, 20% of data was held for testing and so on.

	Splitting criteria [0.9,0.1]	Splitting criteria [0.8,0.2]	Splitting criteria [0.7,0.3]
Accuracy	96.5%	96.6%	96.6%
Test error	3.5%	3.4%	3.4%
Weighted precision	96.47%	96.57%	96.52%
Weighted recall	96.53%	96.6%	96.56%
Weighted F-measure	96.3%	96.4%	96.3%

TABLE 2. Evaluation Metrics for different splitting criteria

The decision tree is a gradual algorithm which performs a recursive partitioning for the feature. Each partition is selected gradually by selecting the best split from several possible splits to maximize the information gain of a tree node. The node impurity is a measure of dividing the training data of the labels at the node into relatively homogenous subsets. There are two impurity measures for classification: Gini impurity and Entropy.

Impurity	Formula	Description
Gini impurity	$\sum_{i=1}^C f_i(1 - f_i)$	f_i is the frequency of label i at a node and C is the number of unique labels.
Entropy	$\sum_{i=1}^C -f_i \log(f_i)$	

TABLE 3. Node Impurity Formulas.

We will use splitting criteria (0.8, 0.2) 80% for the training set and 20% held for the testing set and compare the results when using different impurity measures in the following table.

	Gini impurity	Entropy
Time	5:45s	5:58s
Accuracy	96.53%	96.6%
Test error	3.5%	3.4%
Weighted precision	96.55%	96.52%
Weighted recall	96.52%	96.57%
Weighted F-measure	96.29%	96.34%

TABLE 4. Evaluation Metrics for Node Impurity.

Fig. 3: Evaluation Metrics for Node Impurity

VII. CONCLUSION

This research applied a decision tree classification model on NYC Taxi and Limousine Commission dataset to predict payment type. The dataset contains detailed taxi trips, and each trip record describes the vendor of the data record, passenger count, pickup and drop-off location and timestamp and detailed receipt. The experiment shows a promising result as the accuracy and other evaluation metrics is higher than 96%. For future work, the Decision tree classification model can be applied to the same dataset to predict passenger count, rush hour to predict extra charges, and high demand in a specific time zone. Also, this model can be applied to car services in Egypt like Uber and Careem.

References

- [1] "An introduction to big data", *Opensource.com*, 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://opensource.com/resources/big-data>. [Accessed: 13-Sep- 2018].
- [2] Che, D., Safran, M. and Peng, Z.. (2013). From Big Data to Big Data Mining: Challenges, Issues, and Opportunities. *Database Systems for Advanced Applications*. 7827, 1-15.
- [3] L. Joseji, "6 Sparkling Features of Apache Spark! - DZone Big Data", *dzone.com*, 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://dzone.com/articles/6-sparkling-features-apache>. [Accessed: 24- Sep- 2018].
- [4] H. Karau and R. Warren, *High performance Spark*. O'Reilly Media, 2017, pp. 219 - 251.
- [5] H. Sharma and S. Kumar, "A Survey on Decision Tree Algorithms of Classification in Data Mining", *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 2094-2097, 2016.
- [6] F. Wang, "Analysis of NYC Yellow Taxi data", *NYC Data Science Academy Blog*, 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://nycdatascience.com/blog/student-works/analysis-of-nyc-yellow-taxi-data/>. [Accessed: 11- Nov- 2018].
- [7] M. Yazici, C. Kamga and A. Singhal, "A Big Data Driven Model for Taxi Drivers' Airport Pick-up Decisions in New York City", *2013 IEEE International Conference on Big Data*, pp. 37-44, 2013.
- [8] S. Singh and M. Giri, "Comparative Study Id3, Cart and C4.5 Decision Tree Algorithm: A Survey", *International Journal of Advanced Information Science and Technology (IIAIST)*, vol. 3, no. 7, pp. 47-52, 2014.
- [9] H. Sun and S. McIntosh, "Big Data Mobile Services for New York City Taxi Riders and Drivers", *IEEE International Conference on Mobile Services*, pp. 57-64, 2016.
- [10] X. Meng, J. Bradley, B. Yavuz, E. Sparks, S. Venkataraman, D. Liu, J. Freeman, D. Tsai, M. Amde, S. Owen, D. Xin, R. Xin, M. J. Franklin, R. Zahed, M. Zaharia and A. Talwalkar, "MLlib: Machine Learning in Apache Spark", *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 17, pp. 1235-1241, 2016.
- [11] S. Salloum, R. Dautov, X. Chen, P. Peng and J. Huang, "Big data analytics on Apache Spark", *International Journal of Data Science and Analytics*, vol. 1, no. 3-4, pp. 145-164, 2016.
- [12] [Dataset] "NYC Taxi & Limousine Commission - Trip Record Data", *Nyc.gov*, 2018. [Online]. Available: http://www.nyc.gov/html/tlc/html/about/trip_record_data.shtml. [Accessed: 22- Sep- 2018].
- [13] K. Zhao, D. Khryashchev, J. Freire, C. Silva and H. Vo, "Predicting Taxi Demand at High Spatial Resolution: Approaching the Limit of Predictability", *IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*, pp. 833-842, 2016.
- [14] V. Chaurasia and S. Pal, "A Novel Approach for Breast Cancer Detection using Data Mining Techniques", *International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 2456 - 2465, 2014.
- [15] A. Linden and P. Yarnold, "Using data mining techniques to characterize participation in observational studies", *Journal of Evaluation in Clinical Practice*, vol. 22, no. 6, pp. 839-847, 2016.
- [16] T. Bahari and M. Elayidom, "An Efficient CRM-Data Mining Framework for the Prediction of Customer Behaviour", *International Conference on Information and Communication Technologies*, vol. 46, pp. 725-731, 2015.
- [17] Y. SONG and Y. LU, "Decision tree methods: applications for classification and prediction", *Shanghai Arch Psychiatry.*, pp. 130-135, 2015.